

TRANSFORMATION OF INNOVATIVE BANKING MARKETING IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION OF THE BANKING SERVICES MARKET

Gaidukovych D.

*Ph.D. (Economics), Independent Researcher and Associate Professor,
California, Los Angeles, USA*

Abstract

This article examines the key aspects of the transformation of innovative banking marketing under the influence of the digitalization of the banking services market. The study analyzes the evolutionary changes in the marketing mix and provides a comparative characterization of traditional and innovative marketing approaches in the banking sector. Particular attention is given to identifying future directions for research regarding the necessity for banks to develop a consistent strategy for marketing banking innovations.

Keywords: bank, banking product, marketing, marketing mix, innovation, digitalization, strategy.

Problem Statement

In the context of the transformation of national economies toward digital models, the efficient organization of the movement and redistribution of resources in their monetary form occupies a central role. Global economic trends clearly demonstrate the objective necessity of ensuring the innovative development of banks as a prerequisite for their survival amid financial instability and for the enhancement of economic potential. The relevance and significance of this issue in the banking services market are further evidenced by the ongoing academic and practical discourse on marketing strategies for banking innovations.

Relevance of the Study

The relevance of this study is also driven by the fact that current trends in the theory and practice of marketing banking innovations necessitate the development of new approaches to utilizing the marketing mix throughout the entire life cycle of innovations—from the generation of an innovative idea to the product's market implementation. The advancement of digital technologies has increased banks' attention to the opportunities offered by digital banking innovations. The innovation-driven nature of modern economic processes imposes new demands on the content, methods, and forms of organizing various types of managerial activities related to the marketing of banking innovations.

Literature Review

The prospects of economic digitalization highlight the need for the development and promotion of approaches to marketing banking innovations aimed at supporting banking businesses and orienting their innovative marketing activities not only toward internal capabilities but also toward market needs. This includes the creation of specialized marketing tools for innovation implementation.

The concept of the “digital economy” emerged from the theoretical work of D. Bell in the 1960s, who introduced the idea of an “information economy.” With the development of communication technologies, researchers such as M. Castells proposed the concepts of the “network society” or “network economy” [The concept of a “Digital Economy”]. Since the beginning of the 21st century, both academics and practitioners have widely adopted the term “digital economy.”

According to T. Mesenbourg [Mesenbourg, 2001], the concept of the digital economy can be divided into three key components: (1) the supporting infrastructure

(hardware and software); (2) e-business (conducting economic and other business processes through computer networks); and (3) e-commerce (distribution of goods via the Internet).

H. Karcheva emphasizes that the digital economy is an innovative and dynamic economy based on the active implementation of innovations and information technologies across all types of economic activity and spheres of social life. This enables increased efficiency, competitiveness of the economy, and an improved standard of living for the population [Karcheva et al., 2017, p. 14]. The fundamental principles of the digital economy include: accessibility, purposefulness, independence, freedom of information dissemination, openness and cooperation, standardization, trust and security, and comprehensiveness.

In the banking services market, the volume of payments made through digital channels continues to grow, and the demand for such services remains consistently high. This primarily involves digital technologies, products, and services that are now considered among the most innovative trends in the current development of society, including BioTech, NanoTech, RetailTech, FinTech, LegalTech, InsurTech, and GovTech [Kraus N. et al., 2018]. Considering digital products and services such as blockchain, digital marketing, CRM & BPM systems, grid technologies, and digital insurance, it can be stated that these technologies are transforming the structure and role of marketing.

Based on the studies dedicated to market transformation by J. Moore [Moore, 2006], C. Christensen and M. Raynor [Christensen and Raynor, 2004], and P. Drucker [Drucker, 1998], the emergence of innovation should be viewed as a process of changing market structures. The process of commercializing banking innovations in the context of the digital economy calls for the development of innovative approaches that align marketing activities with market needs and promote the use of digital marketing tools [Kovalenko V. et al., 2023].

The purpose of this research is to substantiate the transformational changes in the marketing mix of banking innovations under the conditions of economic digitalization. The marketing of banking innovations includes several components. First and foremost, it involves project marketing, idea generation, identification of research directions, identification of promising R&D projects, assessment of their market

and investment attractiveness, market launch, and evaluation of maturity stages. Competitive advantages are gained by those banks that actively implement innovative products, enhance the personalization of customer relationships through internet technologies, accelerate the process of building customer loyalty, and reduce operational costs by automating and digitalizing transactions, calculations, and management processes. In order to effectively leverage the potential of digital technologies, banks must adapt existing marketing tools and introduce new ones.

The combination of marketing factors that accompany the delivery of a product to the end consumer at all stages of the process, aimed at eliciting the desired positive market response, is known as the 4P marketing mix. The marketing mix refers to a set of controllable tools, methods, and actions used by producers to influence the market, stimulate the desired response from the target market, and regulate demand for their product. It includes all necessary product parameters that the marketer manages and develops to ensure successful market positioning. In this study, we will refer to it by its abbreviated name: “4P.”

The marketing support of banking innovation implementation is carried out through marketing methodologies that generate key insights about customers (both current and potential users of innovative banking technologies, products, and services), competitors, and the external environment.

Moreover, innovations also include traditional banking products that have been modified under the influence of digitalization, as well as marketing information and communication technologies that provide clients with unique opportunities to meet their banking needs more effectively. These are qualitatively new

products capable of satisfying previously unmet demands of potential consumers. As such, since banking innovations require continuous marketing support in the market, there is a growing need to modify traditional and develop new, specialized technologies for such support.

The systemic analysis of the interdependence between new banking products and the marketing technologies supporting them shows that marketing methods themselves should also become the object of innovation marketing. This is because they create opportunities for the positioning and promotion of new banking products in the financial market, aligning with the objectives of modern marketing development.

The analysis of the nature and features of the concepts of banking innovation marketing and innovation marketing indicates a close relationship between their goals, tasks, and principles. Innovation marketing, based on traditional marketing techniques, increasingly requires the application of new marketing technologies. In this way, it creates the foundation for the further development of innovative marketing. The key difference between the two concepts lies in the subject of influence:

- Innovation marketing is based on the development of innovative banking products through the consistent application and enhancement of marketing mix components;
- Innovative marketing is a broader concept, where the object of influence is innovative marketing technologies themselves. Banking innovation marketing is a subset of this broader category and requires the continuous evolution of these technologies (see Table1).

Table 1.

Comparative Characteristics of Innovation Marketing and Innovative Marketing in Banks

Comparison Criterion	Innovation Marketing	Innovative Marketing
Interpretation	Use of traditional marketing mix tools at the initial stage, with gradual improvement and adaptation of innovative elements	A modern direction in marketing formed on the basis of innovative methods and technologies in banking marketing
Subject of Influence	Innovative banking products, services, and technologies at all stages of the innovation process	Marketing of innovative technologies at all stages of the innovation process or at all stages of the banking product life cycle
Definition of Concepts	Innovation marketing is the management of processes related to the development and implementation of new banking products, aimed at improving the efficiency of using innovative marketing tools, as well as the potential capabilities and resources of banks to meet customer needs and generate profit	Innovative marketing in banking is a separate direction of modern marketing (a concept) that is based on the application of innovative methods and technologies. It develops marketing tools and takes into account the specific influence of digital transformation in creating new products and services

Source: Compiled by the author using materials from [Ivashenko, S. M., 2008; Sakharov, V. E., and Milovidova, Yu. S., 2011]

The main objectives of innovation marketing lie in ensuring that newly developed and proposed innovative banking products and services possess clear value and usefulness for potential customers, who must be properly informed about them. This, in turn, requires the application of innovative marketing technologies.

These objectives are achieved through the use of marketing mix methods, which were first introduced in 1953 by Neil Borden, then President of the American Marketing Association (2001), further refined by Jerome McCarthy (1993), and subsequently developed by Philip Kotler (2009). It is worth noting that the “4P

marketing mix” model is continually being expanded by modern researchers.

Later, the concepts of “5P” and “7P” were developed to provide a more detailed and comprehensive understanding of the original “4P” model (see Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Transformation of the 4P Marketing Mix Concept

Source: compiled by the author based on materials from [Kotler, F., 2009; Carniel, A., 2019].

Under the influence of information and communication technologies, in 1990 B. Lauterborn proposed the “4C” model, in which the focus of marketing technologies shifted from the product to the customer. That is, the emphasis was placed not so much on the product

and its development, but rather on the consumer and the benefits they receive [Lauterborn, B., 1990, p. 28]. The general structure of this transformation is presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Transformation of the 4P Marketing Mix into the 4C Model

Elements of the 4P Mix	Elements of the 4C Model
Product	Consumer
Place	Convenience
Price	Cost
Promotion	Communication

Source: compiled by the author

Supporters of the “4C” marketing model emphasize that consumers value benefit, low total cost, convenience, and communication — rather than traditional promotion. Given the specific nature of banking products and marketing, it is important to note that the 4C model complements — but does not replace — the fundamental principles of the traditional 4P marketing mix. There are several considerations that support this position.

First, the traditional marketing mix, consisting of the 4Ps, also accounts for consumer preferences. When forming the elements of product, price, promotion, and distribution, marketers study and consider customer expectations. Second, according to the 4C model, marketers should indeed focus on customer value. However, in the process of marketing mix transformation under the influence of digitalization in the financial market, banks also take into account the interests of competitors, investors, and stakeholder audiences — not just customers. Third, the 4C model implies managing the behavior of the consumer. Yet a bank customer is not a fully controllable element of the external environment. Banks can influence customer behavior not directly, but indirectly — through updating product offerings, adjusting prices and fees, and offering attractive distribution channels and service delivery formats.

All the additions made by the 4C approach are fundamentally based on the core elements of the 4P model: product, price, place, and promotion. Depending on the strategic goals of banking marketing, additional elements may be incorporated to help guide customer choices. An optimal 4P mix under digitalization should create a combination of marketing tools that ensures the achievement of strategic goals while making rational use of the available marketing budget. The relative significance of each individual marketing mix element depends on a variety of factors affecting the activities of modern banks.

Digital technologies allow banks to expand their product range and create qualitatively new virtual products that are delivered digitally — thereby enlarging the “product” segment of the marketing mix. The importance of the “promotion” element is also increasing. Social media and direct communication with customers have enabled marketers to significantly expand the reach of their target audiences. The influence of digital advertising has grown to such an extent that proposals for international regulation of advertising have been raised (Gil C. V. L., 2001, p. 664).

Under today’s banking conditions, an adaptive approach to the marketing mix is required. This approach is characterized by the situational adaptation of the marketing mix to the digital transformation of banking products. Each bank must carefully analyze the structure of every variable included in the 4P marketing mix, taking into account the specifics of its operations and target audience. After this, it is essential to determine which marketing mix components are controllable and which lie outside the bank’s sphere of influence.

This process leads to the formation of an adapted approach to identifying the bank’s needs in specific marketing tools, based on three types of variables: basic variables — the traditional components of the marketing mix: product, price, place, promotion; independent

components — subcomponents of the basic variables that, considering the bank’s specifics, are logically treated as independent; and derived variables — constructed by combining independent components (or even basic ones), when such combinations are reasonable.

This confirms the need for continuous improvement of the existing theoretical and conceptual framework for developing the 4P marketing mix. However, depending on its goals, a bank may emphasize one element over another, and, if necessary, use elements from other marketing models — if it contributes to more effective implementation of strategic marketing objectives related to innovation in banking.

The results of this research indicate that further scientific study is required to clarify the theoretical aspects of forming and developing innovation marketing in the banking sector, as well as the methodological foundations for analyzing how modern marketing concepts influence the organization of processes related to the development and promotion of new banking products and services based on selected marketing mix elements. A strong scientific foundation for these questions will support the creation of effective conceptual approaches for developing and implementing innovation marketing strategies. The design and implementation of an effective banking innovation marketing strategy contributes to the timely launch of new products and services, creating competitive advantages. Therefore, the use of conceptual approaches by banks in shaping an innovation marketing strategy — one that focuses on meeting both current and future customer needs — reduces financial uncertainty and the risks of consumer rejection of new banking products.

References

1. The concept of a “Digital Economy”. <http://odec.org.uk/the-concept-of-digital-economy>.
2. Mesenbourg, T. L. (2001): Measuring the digital economy. U.S. Bureau of the Census. <https://www.census.gov/econ/estats/papers/umdigital.pdf>.
3. Karcheva, G. T., Ogorodnya, D. V., Openko, V. A. (2017): Digital economy and its impact on the development of the national and international economy. *Financial space*, 3 (27), 13–21.
4. Kraus, N. M., Holoborodko, O. P., Kraus, K. M. (2018): Digital economy: trends and prospects of avant-garde development. *Effective economy*, 1. www.economy.nayka.com.ua.
5. Moore, J. A. (2006): Bridging the gap: marketing and sales of hi-tech products for the mass consumer / Trans. with English Moscow: Williams.
6. Kristinsen, K. M., Raynor, M. E. (2004): Solving the problem of innovations in business. How to create a growing business and successfully support ego growth. Trans. with English Moscow: Alpina Business Books.
7. Drucker, P. (1998): *Effective management. Economic tasks and optimal solutions*. Trans. with English M. Kotelnikova. Moscow: FAIR-PRESS.
8. Kovalenko, V., Sheludko, S., Cherkashyna, K. (2023): Digital transformation of banking business present and future. *Socio-Economic relations in the*

digital society, 4 (50), 25-40.
<https://doi.org/10.55643/ser.4.50.2023.539>.

9. Ilyashenko, S. M. (2008): Marketing of innovations and innovations in marketing: monograph. Sumy: University Book.

10. Sakharov, V. E., Milyutina, Yu. S. (2011): Interpretation, application and development of the conceptual apparatus: marketing of innovations and innovative marketing. Current problems of economics, 5 (119), 122–129.

11. Borden, N. (2001): Marketing mix concept. “Classics of marketing: A collection of works that had the greatest impact on marketing”. Trans. with English under the editorship Yu. N. Kapturevskiy. St. Petersburg: Peter.

12. McCarthy, E. Je., Perreault, W. D. Jr. (1993): Basic Marketing: A Global-Managerial Approach. Professional Publishing (R.D. Irwin).

13. Kotler, F., Caslione, J. A. (2009): Chaotic: management and marketing in the era of turbulence. Trans. from English, ed. T. V. Spivakovskaya, S. V. Spivakovskiy. Kyiv: Khimzhest, PLASKE.

14. Kotler, F. (2009): Marketing management. St. Petersburg: Peter.

15. Carniel, A. (2019): The ultimate guide to marketing mix: 4Ps, 7Ps, 8Ps, 4Cs, 7Cs. <https://www.albertocarniel.com/post/marketing-mix>.

16. Lauterborn, B. (1990): New Marketing Litany: Four Ps Passé: C-Words Take Over. Advertising Age.

17. Gil, C. V. L. (2001): International business in the global market. Translated from English. Kyiv: “Publishing house of Solomiya Pavlychko “Osnovy”.